

Determining Selected Essential Element and Nutritional Composition of Maize Variety and Soil Fertility Status of Cultivated Land Abala Abay Woreda Wolaita Zone, South Ethiopia

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Abstract

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the most widely cultivated cereal crops in the world. The objective of this study was determining the level of essential metal and nutritional composition of maize variety and selected soil fertility status of cultivated land of Abala Abay woreda. The three replicated samples of maize variety (Shone-19, BH540, and BH545) and soil sample were collected from three selected kebel of Abala Abay woreda. The study was conduct at slightly acidic soil, moderate SOC, low to moderate P, high CEC and optimum level of Ca, Mg, K and Na and clay loam textural class. The mean proximate composition of three varieties (BH540, BH545 and Shone-19) was $3.6 \pm 0.3\%$ (fat), $1.8 \pm 0.1\%$ (fiber), $13.2 \pm 1.3\%$ (moisture), $1.14 \pm 0.1\%$ (ash), $7.65\% \pm 0.5$ (protein), 72.5 ± 1.7 kca (carbohydrate) and $353.3 \text{ kcal} \pm 4$ (energy). In current studies, the average selected macro and micro essential metal for three maize varieties ranges 38.3 ± 3.7 mg/kg (Fe), 34.5 ± 1.6 mg/kg (Zn), 0.5 ± 0.03 mg/kg (Co), 3.4 ± 0.22 mg/kg (Mn) for micro essential metal, and 588 ± 26.9 mg/kg (Ca), 496 ± 22.8 mg/kg (Mg), 799 ± 26.3 mg/kg (K), and 162 ± 4.1 mg/kg (Na) for selected macro essential metal. The level of essential metal and nutritional composition of Shone-19, BH540 and BH545 were optimum compared to standard limit of FAO at 2011. From this studied of maize varieties, Shone-19 variety was more preferable for consumption than BH540 and BH545 varieties because of better nutrition composition value and metals concentration.

Keywords: *Maize Variety, soil fertility, Proximate Analysis, Nutritional composition, Metals, South Ethiopia.*

Introduction

Maize is one the most extensive cultivated and consumed cereal crop in the world and Ethiopia. Maize belongs to family of Poaceae, genus *Zea* and species *Zea mays*-corn. Due to its high flexibility, maize is one of the most significant cereal grains farmed globally in a variety of conditions Maize (*Zea mays* L,) the most important cereal crop in the world, plays a significant role in human nutrition. The most widely grown cereal crops worldwide is maize, followed by rice and wheat. The grass (poaceae) family, namely the genus *Zea* and species *Zea mays*, includes the herbaceous plant known as maize (Abebe and Chandravanshi.et al, 2017). Maize is one of the world's three primary cereal crops. It occupies an important position in world economy and trade as a food, feed and industrial grain crop (Girma.et al, 2005). More maize is produced than any other grain, and it is grown commercially in practically every

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nation on Earth for a variety of purposes. 79% of the world's maize production is currently produced in the United States, China, Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, India, France, Indonesia, South Africa, and Italy (Gwirtz and Garcia-Casals et al., 2014).

Maize demand is projected to increase by 50% worldwide and by 93% in sub-Saharan Africa between 1995 and 2020 (FAO, 2007). Maize is one of the most important cereals broadly adapted worldwide (Christian et al. 2012). It is largely produced in Western, Central, Southern and Eastern parts of Ethiopia. South Africa is the largest producer of maize with about 35% of the total regional production. Nigeria is the second most important producer (Stern et al., 2012). Maize (*Zea mays L.*) is one of the most widely cultivated cereal crops in the world. It is among the staple food crops produced globally. Ethiopia is the fourth largest maize-producing country in Africa (World Bank, 2007).

Maize is one of the most important cereal crops in Ethiopia, ranking second in area coverage after teff and first in total production (CSA, 2013). When it comes to total production and the number of agricultural holdings active in the nation, maize dominates the grain market. Teff and sorghum, the second and third most popular crops in the nation, accounted for 20% and 22%, respectively, of the total cereal production in 2010–11. Maize made up 28% of that total. Ethiopia's largest and most prolific crop is maize. The Central Statistics Agency (CSA) reports that the production of maize was 3.75 million tons in 2007–2008, which was 41% more than sorghum and 25% more than teff. The highest-yielding cereal crops are maize, with a yield of 2.5 tons per hectare. Ethiopia, behind South Africa, Nigeria, and Egypt, is the continent's fourth-largest producer of maize. (World Bank, 2007). So, Ethiopia has a strong potential for expanding maize production through the widespread use of improved seeds, which is happening right now (Dawit et al., 2008).

Throughout the nation, both organic and inorganic fertilizers are employed. Crop waste, livestock dung, and legumes are examples of farm-generated organic fertilizers. The use of inorganic (modern) fertilizer calls for enhanced types of maize seeds, which is a peculiar input. In Ethiopia, the two most extensively used inorganic fertilizers are urea and di ammonium phosphate (DAP) (World Bank, 2007). In Ethiopia, there are numerous varieties of maize, including BH540, BH545 SHONE 19, BH660, BH661, and others. But BH540, BH545, and SHONE19 varieties are used in this study (www.americanmaize.com, 2015; www.starch.dk, 2015; www.corn.org, 2013).

Soil fertility is a key determinant of crop yield and nutritional quality. Monitoring nutrient status for assessing the degree of nutrient mining in an agro-ecosystem is very crucial. The change in soil nutrient stocks over time must be measured to quantify the extent of nutrient status and institute ways of maintaining the cropping system for sustainable crop production (FAO, 2003). Maize productivity in many parts of the country remains below potential due to several interrelated factors, among which soil fertility depletion and nutrient imbalance are critical (Wondowosen and Sheleme, 2011). Thus, there is a need for a more targeted approach to soil fertility intervention that differentiates between farm components, agro-ecological zone and socio-economic group (Elias et al., 1998). Physicochemical properties of soil such as texture, pH, organic matter (OM), cation exchanging capacities (CEC), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), zinc (Zn), and iron (Fe) significantly influence plant growth, grain yield, and the nutritional value of maize. Variations in soil properties, nutrient availability, and agronomic practices contribute to disparities in maize performance across different regions (Wondowosen and Sheleme, 2011). In Abala Abaya Woreda of the Wolaita Zone, maize is a dominant crop cultivated on smallholder farms. However, systematic information on the soil nutrient status and its relationship to the elemental composition of maize varieties grown in the area is limited. Addressing this gap is essential for guiding site-specific nutrient management and enhancing both the yield and nutritional quality of maize. Therefore, understanding the nutrient composition of maize varieties namely (Shone-19, BH-540, and BH-545) and evaluating the fertility status of the soils in which they are grown are crucial steps toward improving productivity and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. This study aimed to assess the

selected essential element content (Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe, Mn, Co, Zn) and proximate composition (moisture, ash, protein, fat, crude fiber, carbohydrate, and energy) of a maize variety cultivated in Abala Abaya Woreda, alongside an evaluation of the fertility status of the associated agricultural soils. The findings are expected to contribute valuable data for integrated soil fertility management and crop improvement strategies tailored to the local context.

The existing knowledge gap regarding the elemental composition and nutritional value of maize in the Wolaita zone hinders the development of effective strategies for promoting food security and addressing potential health risks associated with maize consumption. This research aims to fill this gap by providing accurate and detailed information on the levels of essential metals (Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe, Mn, Co, Zn) and the proximate analysis of moisture, ash, protein, fat, crude fiber, carbohydrate, and energy content in three maize varieties cultivated in selected study areas. There are no further studies done on determination of the nutritional composition of maize varieties namely (Shone-19, BH-540, and BH-545). The objectives of these study were determining level of essential metals (Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe, Mn, Co, Zn) and proximate analysis of moisture, ash, protein, fat, crude fiber, carbohydrate, and energy content of maize varieties.

Methodology

Description of the Study Areas

The study was conducted on some selected areas of the Wolaita zone abala abay woreda in three kebel such as Abala Faracho towns, Konto and Lirans) in south Ethiopia. It is 98 km southeast of Hosanna and 345km from Addis Ababa. This town has altitude and longitude of 7°8'39"N, 37°57'20"E with an elevation of 1958m above sea level. Abala Abay woreda is one of the woredas in Wolaita zone, south Ethiopia. Abala Faracho town is another woreda in the Wolaita zone. It is 92 kilometers southeast of Hosanna and 357 kilometers from Addis Ababa. It is a part of triangle-shaped exclave of the Wolaita zone and bordered on the south by the Wolaita zone, on the north by the Kembata Tambero zone. This town has a latitude and longitude of 7.1359°N and 37.8353°E, with an elevation of 1961 m (6433.73 feet) above sea level.

Figure 1. Arc GIS Map of Abala Abay Woreda Woaita Zone, Ethiopia

Soil Sample Collection, Preparation and Analysis

The soil samples were collected in 2014 and 2015 cropping seasons from three sampling site of Abala Abay woreda of maize farmers' fields per season. Random sampling was employed to collect soil samples from the three sampling sites from 0-20cm depth. Soil and maize samples were collected from the same field. From each site three farmers were randomly selected, and composite soil samples were taken. A total of nine representative composite soil samples were taken to Areka agricultural research center soil laboratory. Then, the samples were air-dried, crushed, and sieved using a 2 mm sieve before analysis. The soil pH was measured with digital pH meter potentiometrically in the supernatant suspension of 1:2.5 soils to water (Okalebo.et al., 2002). Soil Organic carbon was determined following wet digestion method as described by Wackily and Black (1934), whereas the Kjeldal procedure was used for the determination of total nitrogen (N) as described by Jackson (1958). The available phosphorus (P) was measured by the Olsen method as described by Olsen.et al (1954). The CEC and exchangeable base Ca, Mg, K and Na analyzed by 1N NH₄OAC leachate and former by kjeldal distillation followed by titration and later Ca and mg with AAS and Na and K by Flame photometer (Morgan, 1986). The physical parameter which was particle size distribution analyzed by Calgon solution (NaPO₃) as dispersing agent and read by hydrometer (Bouyoucos.et al, G. H, 1951).

Sample Collection of Maize

The maize seed samples were collected randomly from the farmlands of three selected Woreda (K001, K002 and K003 (Abala Faracho towns) in Wolaita zone. The nine samples were collected from each woreda and a total of 27 maize samples collected from three maize varieties at study areas. From three maize varieties such as BH540, BH545 and Shone 19 about 100g of raw and dry samples were collected from selected woreda, kebel and farmers. These three maize varieties from each kebel in woreda were mixed and made to one composite maize variety. The collected maize sample was labeled and tags to precede sample preparation and laboratory analysis at southern agricultural research institute areka agricultural research center soil, plant and water analysis laboratory.

Samples Digestion

2 g of well-powdered maize flour or homogenized, dried, and ground maize samples were transferred into 250-mL round-bottom flasks. Then the mixture of HNO₃ (69–72%), HClO₄ (60%) and H₂O₂ (30%) with a volume ratio was added, and the mixture was digested on a Kjeldahl digestion apparatus for the optimized period of time at the optimized temperature.

Proximate Analysis

The proximate analysis of raw maize variety samples were determined in triplicate according to the procedure described by the (AOAC, 2005).

Determination of Moisture Content

Moisture is one of the most important components of food. The (AOAC, 2005) a method was used to determine the moisture content of maize varieties, which was done in a 202-1B drying oven at 105°C for 1 hour and calculated as:

$$\% \text{Moisture content} = \frac{\text{Weight loss of maize}}{\text{Weight of the orinal maize}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Determination of Ash Content

Two grams of the dried sample were weighed into a dry porcelain dish and then heated in a muffle furnace at 600°C for two hours (using a box-type resistance (SX2-4-1 OJ) muffle furnace at 550°C overnight). The crucibles with the samples were transferred directly from the furnace into a desiccator,

which allowed them to cool while their weight was taken. Ash content was determined by the method of (AOAC, 2005).

$$\% \text{ Ash content} = \frac{\text{Weight of ash}}{\text{Weight of the original maize}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Determination of Fat Content

The fat content of the maize samples was estimated using a crude ether extract of moisture-free samples using Soxhlet's Extraction Method on the Socs plus System (Sextet 8000 extraction equipment). The extraction time of the soxhlet was adjusted to 15 minutes, 30 minutes, and 10 minutes for boiling, rising, and recovery times, respectively. The extracted and residual solvents were dried in an oven and weighed after cooling in desiccators. Fat content was determined by the method of (AOAC, 2005).

$$\% \text{ Crude fat content} = \frac{\text{Extracted fat of Maize}}{\text{Weight of maize sample}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Determination Crude Protein

The protein content was calculated by measuring the nitrogen content of the sample using the Micro-kejdal Method. The protein content of the products was calculated by multiplying the nitrogen content of the material by a factor of 6.25 (general factor). The nitrogen content was determined using the following formula (NIN, 2003).

$$\text{Percent Nitrogen } \% = \frac{\text{ml HCl in determination} - \text{ml blank} \times \text{Normality of HCl}}{\text{Weight of maize sample}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

(Crude protein content (g) = Percent Nitrogen *6.25

Determination of Crude Fiber

The crude fiber of maize varieties was determined using the Fibertec TM 8000 auto fiber analysis system, and the percentage of crude fiber was calculated as follows: (AOAC, 2005).

$$\% \text{ Crude fiber} = \frac{W2 - (W3 + C)}{W1} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Where, W1 is weight of sample, W2 is weight of (crucible + residue), W3 is weight of (crucible + ash residue) and C is blank.

Determination of Carbohydrate Content

Total carbohydrates were calculated by subtracting from 100 the sum of the crude protein, fat, ash, and crude fiber values (per 100g). The following formula is used to calculate total carbohydrate content (AOAC, 2005; NIN, 2003).

$$\text{Carbohydrate (g/100g)} = 100 - (\text{moisture} + \text{crude fiber} + \text{ash} + \text{crude protein} + \text{fat}) \quad (6)$$

Determination of Energy

The samples' energy values were calculated using physiological fuel values of 4 kcal per gram for protein, 9 kcal per gram for fat, and 4 kcal per gram for carbohydrates (AOAC, 2005; NIN, 2003).

$$\text{Energy (Kcal/100g)} = [(\% \text{ protein} \times 4) + (\% \text{ carbohydrates} \times 4) + (\% \text{ fat} \times 9)] \quad (7)$$

Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed statistically using analysis of variance (ANOVA) (SAS version 9.1.3). The Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test was used at p 0.05 to determine significant differences in the amount of all parameter of soil and maize at three sampling sites. Pearson's correlation analysis was also applied to test the correlation between elements within maize seed samples. For each selected element,

the mean concentration value was compared with the maximum permissible limit set by WHO/FAO using a one-sample t-test at a 95% confidence interval. All statistical analyses were done with SPSS and SAS software.

Results and Discussion

Determination of Soil Fertility Status of Study Site

The soil physiochemical parameter of study site was determined using standard analytical techniques and procedure. The pH of soil at study site was ranged from 6 to 6.34 and average pH result was 6.12 ± 0.16 and result shows that soil of study site was slightly acidic according to Tekalign rating (Tekalign, 1991). The concentration of SOC and total nitrogen in study site ranges from 2.3 to 2.83 % and 0.11 to 0.13 % respectively and average results of SOC and TN was 2.59 ± 0.24 and 0.12 ± 0.008 respectively. The level SOC in soil of study was moderate but the amount of TN in soil was low and less adequate for most crop production (Booker, 1991, Murphy, 1968). The concentration of available phosphorus was done in Olsen methods (Olsen, 1954) and the concentration of P in soil of study areas was ranges from 8.6 to 10.43ppm and average phosphorus was 9.32 ± 0.64 ppm. The average concentration p in study site indicates soil had low to moderate phosphorus concentration in soil of study areas according to ETHIOS soil map of 2017 and Olsen rating of 1954. The amount of CEC and exchangeable base Ca, Mg, K and Na were analyzed by !N NH₄OAC, the Ca and Mg read in AAS and later two Na and K with Flame photometer, and CEC in Kedjal distillation follow by titration. The amount of CEC soil of study areas ranges from 28.6 to 35.2 meq/100g and average amount of CEC was 31.84 ± 1.724 meq/100g and result indicate that level of CEC at all study site was high according to Beranu.et al (1980) and Booker (1991). The average level exchangeable base Ca and Mg was 18.84 ± 1.15 and 4.05 ± 0.25 meq/100g soil respectively and result was high according to ETHIOSIS map 2017 and study was in line with ATA 2017. The average concentration of K and Na was 2.17 ± 0.13 and 1.59 ± 0.095 meq/100g and result was optimum according to rating of Tekalign.et al (1991) and Beranu.et al (1980). The physical parameter of soil which particle size distribution of study areas was sand, clay and silt were analyzed by Hydrometer. The average result of percent of sand, clay and silt was 39.7 ± 1.67 , 41.4 ± 2.07 and $18.9 \pm 1.8\%$ respectively and soil has clay loam textural classes.

From soil analysis and ANOVA table, the parameters such as SOC, available P, CEC and percentage of Clay were statistical significance between sample or Kebel at 95% confidence interval due to that p value less than 0.0show Table 1 below. But others parameter such as pH, TN, %Sand, %Silt, Ca, Mg, K and Na were non-significant at 95% CI due to the P value greater than 0.05 and even the soil data was statistical non-significant there was numerical difference between soil at study site. The Reason for difference results was material in which soil develop, soil formation, material used, management difference across farmers and natural cases.

Table 1. The ANOVA Table of Soil Physiochemical Parameter of Abala Abay Woredda

Kebele	pH	% OC	% TN	P Ppm	CEC	% Sand	% Clay	% Silt	Ca	Mg	K	Na
K001	6.00	2.83	0.11	8.60	28.6	40	42.7	17.3	18.6	4.00	2.14	1.57
K002	6.02	2.63	0.13	10.43	32.1	39	39	22	18.9	4.06	2.18	1.6
K003	6.34	2.30	0.12	8.93	35.2	40	42.7	17.3	19.1	4.09	2.19	1.61
Mean	6.12 ± 0.16	2.59± 0.24	0.12± 0.008	9.32± 0.64	31.84 ± 1.724	39.67 ± 1.67	41.4± 2.07	18.9 ± 1.8	18.84 ± 1.15	4.05 ± 0.25	2.17 ± 0.13	1.59 ± 0.1

CV	4.46	15.82	12.27	12.03	10.43	7.28	8.63	16.55	10.53	10.42	10.40	10.5
P (<0.05)	0.23	0.019	0.51	0.024	0.04	0.068	0.036	0.67	0.85	0.87	0.96	0.81

Note: CV: coefficient of variation, CEC, Ca, Mg, K and Na were in unit of meq/100g

Determination of Essential Metal in Maize Variety

The amount of essential metal and trace element was determined in different maize variety follow standard analytical techniques and methods. The result was reported as mean value from triplicate analysis of each sample to check the accuracy and precision of the results and reported as the mean value plus or minus SD for all metals in the study.

The Concentration of Macro and Micro Essential Metal

The concentration Macro-essential metals that were absorbed by different maize varieties accumulated at different parts of the plant, such as the root, stem, seed, and flower parts, but the study focused only on the seed part of different maize varieties. There was a difference in the concentration of macro-essential metals in selected maize varieties. Among the studied macro elements, K had the highest concentration compared to others such as Ca, Mg, and Na. The level of K ranged from 740 to 905 mg/kg, with the highest concentration of K observed at variety Shone-19 (D-sh-19, 905 mg/kg) and the lowest at variety one (YBH540, 740.2) dry matter base, followed by Ca and Mg levels. The concentration of Ca ranges from 510.7 to 700.3 mg/kg, with the lowest level of Ca observed at variety one (YBH540, 510.7 mg/kg) and highest at variety nine (D-SH19, 700 mg/kg). The level of Mg ranges from 432 to 590 mg/kg, with the lowest concentration observed at variety one (YBH540, 432) and highest at variety nine (D-SH-19, 590 mg/kg). The sodium concentration ranges from 148 ppm (BH545) to 183 ppm (A-BH545).

Table 2. The Essential and Trace Element Analysis of Three Maize Varieties at Three Woreda

S/ code	Fe	Zn	Co	Mn	Ca	Mg	K	Na
YBH540	31.35	29	0.53	3.2	510.7	432	740.2	170
KoBH545	39.11	42.6	0.44	2.7	530	469.8	758	148
DSH19	46.19	27.6	0.47	2.7	700	590	905	176
Mean	38.8 \pm 7.4	33.1 \pm 8.3	0.5 \pm 0.05	2.9 \pm 0.3	580.2 \pm 104.2	497 \pm 82.5	801.1 \pm 90.4	106 \pm 15.6
CV	19.1	25.1	9.5	10.1	18.0	16.6	11.3	14.7
BSH19	47.27	40.6	0.49	2.8	556	482.5	789	157
KBH545	38.1	32.6	0.45	2.6	490	400	720	142
K*BH540	31.23	26.2	0.43	2.5	610	516.3	807	160
Mean	38.87 \pm 8.1	33.1 \pm 7.2	0.46 \pm 0.1	2.63 \pm 0.2	552 \pm 60	516.3 \pm 59.8	772 \pm 46	153 \pm 9.6
CV	20.7	31.8	6.7	5.8	10.9	12.8	5.9	6.3
ABH545	31.4	31.4	0.63	4	650	528.3	820	183
LBH540	37.16	37.4	0.56	3.1	580	496	795.3	153
MSH19	43.1	38.4	0.51	3	670	550	860	169
Mean	37.2 \pm 6	35.7 \pm 3.8	0.57 \pm 0.06	3.37 \pm 0.6	633.3 \pm 47.3	524 \pm 27.1	825.1 \pm 32.7	168.3 \pm 15
CV	15.7	10.6	10.6	16.4	7.5	5.2	4.0	8.9

Note: D-SH19, YBH540 and Ko-BH545 from K001 kebel; BSH-19, K* BH545 and K-BH540 from K002 kebel and M-SH-19; ABH545 and L-BH540 from Abala Faracho town (K003 kebel) and all parameter in ppm

The micro-essential elements of the current study were Fe, Co, Mn, and Zn. From these selected micro-essential metals analyzed, Fe was most abundant in the selected maize variety. The level of iron at selected maize varieties ranges from 31.5 to 46.19 mg/kg, with the lowest concentration found at variety BH545 (K*BH545, 31.23 mg/kg) and the highest at variety SH-19 (D-SH-19, 46.19 mg/kg), followed by Zn and

Mn (table 4). The concentration of cobalt at maize varieties ranges from x to y, with the maximum Co level observed at variety BH545 (ABH545, 0.63 ppm) and the lowest at variety BH540 (k*BH540, 0.43 ppm). The level of Mn nutrient at selected maize varieties ranges from 2.5 to 4 ppm, with a maximum at sample A-BH545 (A-BH545, 4.0) and a minimum at variety BH540 (k*BH540, 2.5 ppm).

Table 3. Mean Separation of Selected Macro and Micro-Essential Metal of Three Maize Variety (ANOVA, DF = 2)

s/code	Fe	Zn	Co	Mn	Ca	Mg	K	Na
BH545	36.2±4.2 ^a	35.53±6.2 ^b	0.49±0.05 ^a	2.8±0.4 ^a	556.67±83 ^a	466.03±64 ^c	766±50.5 ^c	158.3±11 ^a
BH540	33.25±3.3 ^b	30.87±5.8 ^a	0.46±0.06 ^{ab}	2.7±0.26 ^c	566.9±51 ^b	481.43±44 ^b	780.83±35 ^b	157±13 ^b
SH-19	45.52±2.2 ^{dc}	35.53±6.2 ^{bc}	0.55±0.08 ^c	3.4±0.8 ^d	642±76 ^c	540.83±54 ^a	851.33±59 ^a	170±16 ^b
Mean	38.3±3.7	34±1.55	0.5±0.03	3±0.22	588±26.9	496±22.8	799±26.3	162±4.1
CV	16.2	7.9	9.2	12.8	7.6	8	5.7	4.4
T	10.4	21.8	17	13.3	22	21.8	30.4	39.1
P	0.09	0.002	0.003	0.006	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001
Sign	**	***	***	***	***	***	***	***

Note: CV: coefficient of variation, sign: significance difference, conc of Fe, Zn, Mn, Co, Mg, Ca, Na and K in ppm

The mean separation of macro and micro essential elements in Table 4.4 shows that there was a numerical and statistical difference among selected varieties due to genetic variation and environmental factors. The concentration of potassium was the highest of all the major metals shown in the above table. The level of K ranges from 766±50.5mg/kg to 851.33±59mg/kg dry weight base, followed by Ca, Mg, and Na, respectively. The levels of Ca, Mg, and Na range from 556.67±83 to 642±76, 466.03±64 to 540.83±54, 157±13 to 170±16 ppm, respectively. The order of macro-essential metals studied at the current maize variety order as K>Ca>Mg>Na. From the selected variety, K was highest at the Shone 19 variety (SH-19), which was collected from the D-Sh-19 location and was 905 mg/kg, followed by Shone 19 (M-SH-19, 860 mg/kg).

The level of potassium also has the following order in the variety series: BH-545<BH-540<Shone-19(SH-19). For all macro-essential metals, the Shone 19 variety had the highest concentration compared to the BH-540 and BH-545 varieties. The sample from all locations with the respective variety of maize had a significant difference at the 95% confidence interval and two degrees of freedom because of p<0.05. The level of potassium was lower than previous studies in the Tigray region of Ethiopia because previous study concentrations ranged from 1688 to 1784 mg/kg, but other macro-essential metals such as Ca, Mg, and Na were higher in the current study than previous ones (Abebe, et al., 2017).

The mean separation of micro-essential metals in Table 4.4 shows that Fe was the highest compared to Zn, Mn, and Co. The mean value of iron was highest at the Shone-19 variety, which was 45.2 mg/kg, and lowest at the BH545 variety. The average concentration of micro essential elements had Zn, Mn, and Co at 30.5 to 35.5mg/kg, 2.5 to 4.0 mg/kg, and 0.46 to 0.55 mg/kg, respectively. The order of micro essential elements in the selected maize variety was Fe>Zn>Mn>Co. The shone 19 maize variety had the highest concentration relative to BH540 and BH545 varieties in Fe, Mn, and Co except Zn, which had almost the same level with BH545 and the lowest for BH540 with selected micro-essential metals and a significant difference among the three varieties due to p<0.05.

Proximate Composition of Maize Variety

The determination of the proximate composition of different maize varieties is important so as to detect the varieties that are good sources of the basic nutrients required for the proper growth and development of humans and other animals. The proximate analysis of different maize varieties is shown in Table 4.

The percentage of moisture content ranges from 9.23% to 14.48%, with the highest moisture content from the listed maize content obtained at variety BH540 (14.48%) and the lowest moisture content at variety D-SH-19 (9.23%). The ash percentage was done at dry matter base, and the percentage ranges from 0.77% to 1.8%. The highest ash content was obtained at variety nine (D-SH-19, 1.8%) and the lowest at variety two (BH-545, 0.77%). The composition of different maize varieties' crude protein and carbohydrate ranges from 1.35% to 2.45% and 63.74% to 79.43%, respectively. The maize variety composition for protein implies the highest concentration at variety 9 (D-SH-19, 2.45%) and lowest at variety two (BH545, 1.35%), and for carbohydrate, the highest concentration at variety two (BH545, 79.43%) and lowest at variety 8 (L-SH-540, 63.74%).

According to proximate analysis of maize varieties at the study site for energy, the energy of selected maize varieties ranges from 332 Kcal to 363 Kcal, with and highest energy obtained at variety two (KoBH545, 363 Kcal) and the lowest energy obtained at variety eight (L-SH-19, 332 Kcal) (KoBH545) from K001 and K003 kebele at Abala Faracho town (L-SH-19) respectively.

The moisture content of maize was significant for the stability and quality of food, and high-moisture grains were subjected to rapid deterioration from mold growth and insect damage (Suleiman et al., 2013). And (Sweets, 2018). The moisture content of food is of high economic importance to both the processor and the consumer because the amount of moisture in food is inversely related to the amount of dry matter it contains. When comparing current study moisture content with former study in other Ethiopian regions, current studies had higher moisture contents than former and it ranges from 9.23 to 20.97%, whereas former studies range from 7.6 to 8.0% (Abebe, et al., 2017).

Table 4. Proximate Analysis of Three Maize Varieties at Three Woreda of Wolaita Zone

S/ code	Moisture	Ash	Protein	Fat	C/ fiber	CH ₂ O	Energy
YBH540	14.48	0.97	8.84	4.4	2.12	69.19	351.7
KoBH545	10.13	0.77	5.8	2.51	1.35	79.43	363.52
D-SH-19	9.23	1.8	10.67	3.1	2.45	72.75	361.58
Mean	11.28±2.8	1.18±0.05	8.44±2.5	3.34±0.97	1.97±0.56	73.8±5.2	238.4±8.4
CV	24.8	46.3	29.2	28.98	28.6	7.05	3.5
B-SH-19	14.29	0.93	6.41	4.65	1.65	72.07	355.78
K*BH540	12.87	1.15	6.1	2.89	1.54	75.46	352.24
K-BH545	12.93	1.11	7.95	2.65	1.72	73.64	350.21
Mean	13.4±0.8	1.06±0.12	6.8±0.99	3.4±1.09	1.64±0.09	73.7±1.7	352.7±2.8
CV	6.01	11.02	14.53	32.15	5.54	2.3	0.8
A-BH545	13.12	1.16	6.65	4.12	1.62	73.33	357.01
L-BH540	20.19	1.17	8.14	4.95	1.81	63.74	332.08
M-SH-19	11.92	1.23	8.32	3.16	1.93	73.44	355.48
Mean	15.08±4.5	1.19±0.04	7.7±0.9	4.08±0.9	1.79±0.16	70.17±5.6	348.2±14
CV	29.6	3.2	11.9	22	8.74	7.93	4.02

Note: YBH540, KoBH545 and DSH-19 from K001 kebel, BSH-19, k*BH540, KBH545 from K002 and A-BH545, M-BH540 and L-SH-19 from K003 maize collected farmers

Crude fat is an important component of maize grains, and improvement in fat content aids good human health as it acts as a vehicle for fat soluble vitamins (Reboul.et al., 2017). The percentage crude fat of the three analyzed maize varieties ranged from 3.09 to 4.08%, which was lower than the former ones, which were 1.29±0.01% to 4.25±0.02% (abebe.et al., 2017) and slightly different from 4.07±0.02 reported by Okonkwo and Agharandu (Adaneyi.et al., 2019), who analyzed maize purchased from Umuahia town market in Abia state, Nigeria. Foodstuffs are analyzed for % ash content so as to determine the non-organic matter component of the dry matter, i.e., the remainder after oven drying, ignition, or complete

oxidation of organic matter present in the foodstuff. The ash content gives a rough idea of the total mineral amount present in the food. The ash content ranged from $1.01 \pm 0.01\%$ to $1.320.01\%$, which is higher than the former study of 0.49 to 1.32% studied at Tigray, Ethiopia (Gebrezgi.et al., 2019) and also higher than the former study of Nigeria, 2.19% recorded by (Ape.et al.,2017).

Proteins occasionally provide amino acids (for building and maintaining the body) and energy. They are also used to produce nitrogen-containing substances such as antibodies and enzymes, which are important for normal body functions. Analyzed maize varieties had protein content ranges from 6.8% to 8.4% and an average of 7.65%, which was lower than the study in Ethiopia, which was $8.2 \pm 0.1\%$ (Gebrezri.et al., 2019), and Nigeria, $9.92 \pm 0.02\%$ and $15.75 \pm 0.01\%$; (Okonkwo and Agharandu.et al, 2017) Crude fiber, largely composed of cellulose and hemicellulose, provides beneficial effects in humans by increasing water retention capacity during the passage of food along the gut. A diet rich in crude fiber is considered healthy (Capuano, 2017).because it helps produce larger and softer faces. The result of crude fiber of analyzed maize varieties ranged from $1.56\% \pm 0.01$ to $2.01\% \pm 0.01$; this is slightly lower than values reported by (Gebrezgi.et al., 2019), which were $11.2\% \pm 0.25$. Maize is known to be rich in carbohydrate, and as such, it provides energy, aids in the utilization of body fats through the metabolic process, and helps in the functioning of the intestinal tract.

Table 5. Mean Separation of Three Maize Variety and Significance Test (ANOVA)

S/ code	(%)Moisture	%ash	%protein	%Fat	Crude fiber	CH2O	Energy
BH540	15.8 ± 3.8	1.1 ± 0.1	7.7 ± 1.4	4.1 ± 1.1	1.8 ± 0.3	69.5 ± 5.9	345.3 ± 11.5
BH545	12.1 ± 1.7	1 ± 0.2	6.8 ± 1.1	3.1 ± 0.9	1.6 ± 0.2	75.5 ± 3.4	356.9 ± 6.7
SH-19	13.6 ± 2.5	1.3 ± 0.4	8.5 ± 2.1	3.6 ± 0.9	2 ± 0.4	72.8 ± 0.7	237.1 ± 2
Mean	13.83 ± 2.8	1.13 ± 0.23	7.67 ± 1.53	3.6 ± 0.97	1.8 ± 0.3	72.6 ± 3.3	313.07 ± 6.7
CV	17.6	14.1	10.9	13.7	12.5	4.2	1.9
P	0.007	0.01	0.004	0.006	0.006	0.001	0.000
Sign	***	**	***	***	***	***	***

Note: CV: coefficient of variation

The percentage carbohydrate content of the analyzed maize varieties was observed to fall between 69.5 ± 6 and 75.50 ± 3.4 . This is in accordance with the results reported by (Adeniyi.et al.2017) and 67.01 ± 0.1 according to the report of (Gebrezgi.et al.2019), in which the current study was higher than the former two studies in Ethiopia because at this study carbohydrate ranges from 69.5 (BH545) to 75.52kcal (BH540). The differences observed among the varieties could be due to genetic factors inherent in the different varieties, environmental factors, or agronomic practices with which they were grown.

The mean separation table of the proximate analysis of maize varieties shows whether this different variety had a significant difference or not. From Table 4 above, the average fat content of three maize varieties ranges from 3.1 to 4.1%, with the highest fat content observed at the BH540 variety and the lowest at the BH545 variety. There was also a significant difference among the three varieties because P was less than alpha ($p < 0.05$). The proximate composition among three maize varieties showed that the average composition of crude fiber, moisture, ash, and protein percentage was minimums at the BH545 variety and maximum for shone 19 varieties (SH-19), except for the moisture percentage, which was maximum at the BH540 variety. The proximate composition of maize varieties was significantly different among all varieties due to different genetic variation and environmental factors such as land types, soil types and climate conditions as well as a p value less than alpha.

The protein contents of three maize varieties range from 6.8 to 8.47%, and the average protein contents for the current maize variety were 7.65 ± 0.5 ; the highest protein content was obtained at Shone-19 and the lowest at BH540 maize variety. This may be due to different factors such as soil types, climate factors,

and genetic variation. When comparing current results with previous studies, the average protein content of the current study is lower than the previous ones because the current study has a protein content of 7.65%, while the former study had 8.2%.

Pearson Correlation and Linear Regression of Composition of Maize Variety

The Pearson correlation implies how two variables vary together, or the variability of two variables. The Pearson correlation coefficient (R^2) describes the variance and covariance of variables. According to Table 4.5, the proximate composition variable and essential metal pair fat had a positive and significant correlation with crude fiber, moisture content, and protein, but the level of correlation was different. i.e., moisture content has a strong correlation with fat because $R^2 > 0.75$; crude fiber and protein have a moderate correlation with fat because $R^2 < 0.75$ and greater than 0.5 and Pearson correlation coefficients ($R^2 = 0.8, 0.63, \text{ and } 0.58, p < 0.05, df = 2$), but have a strong and negative correlation with carbohydrate, energy, and Zn with correlation coefficient ($R^2 = -0.99, -0.81, \text{ and } -0.84; p < 0.05, df = 2$) and significant correlation at 95% CI, respectively.

The moisture content of maize varieties had negatively correlated with most variables such as carbohydrate, energy, iron, zinc, Ca, Co, Na, and Mn, with different levels of correlation coefficient. The ash percentage correlates positively and significantly with most variable macro and micro essential metals and protein; the protein also positively and significantly correlates with macro and micro essential metals but negatively with carbohydrate. The iron had a positive and significant correlation with the proximate composition of ash%, fiber, protein, and energy with the Pearson correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.66, 0.88, 0.69, \text{ and } 0.77$), respectively, but negatively and significantly with moisture content ($R^2 = -0.77, df = 3$).

Table 6. Pearson Correlation of Proximate Composition and Essential Metal of Maize Variety

c/Fibre	0.63	1												
Moisture	0.80	0.04	1											
Ash	0.31	0.94	-0.31	1										
Protein	0.58	0.93	0.05	0.95	1									
CH ₂ O	-0.99	-0.53	-0.87	-0.22	-0.48	1								
Energy	-0.81	-0.04	-0.99	0.31	-0.01	0.87	1							
Fe	-0.17	0.66	-0.73	0.88	0.69	0.3	0.77	1						
Zn	-0.84	-0.09	-0.98	0.27	-0.04	0.89	0.98	0.68	1					
Ca	0.17	0.87	-0.45	0.99	0.89	-0.05	0.45	0.94	0.4	1				
Mg	0.25	0.91	-0.37	0.99	0.93	-0.14	0.37	0.89	0.32	0.99	1			
K	0.22	0.89	-0.41	0.98	0.92	-0.1	0.4	0.92	0.35	0.9	0.9	1		
Na	-0.03	0.76	-0.62	0.93	0.79	0.14	0.62	0.98	0.56	0.98	0.96	0.97	1	
Co	0.27	0.58	-0.78	0.83	0.63	0.38	0.79	0.99	0.76	0.9	0.86	0.88	0.97	1
Mn	-0.07	0.73	-0.65	0.93	0.77	0.19	0.65	0.99	0.61	0.97	0.95	0.96	0.99	0.98
	Fat	fiber	%Moist	%ash	%prot	CH ₂ O	Energy	Fe	Zn	Ca	Mg	K	Na	Co

Note: 95%CI: confidence interval, df: 9

Macro- and micro-essential metals such as Fe, Zn, Mn, Co, Ca, K, Mg, and Na were major constituents of maize and important for humans directly and indirectly. The potassium had a positive and significant correlation with %ash, %protein, and %fiber strongly with coefficients ($R^2 = 0.89, 0.98, \text{ and } 0.92$), respectively. And macro and micro essentials such as Fe, Ca, Mg, Na, Mn, and Co had a positive, strong,

and significant correlation with potassium and coefficient ($R^2 = 0.92, 0.9, 0.9, 0.97, 0.96$, and 0.88 , $df = 2$), respectively, as shown in table 8 below.

Figure 2. a) Proximate Composition b) Macro and Micro Essential Metal

The bar graph above shows the proximate composition, macro- and micro-essential elements, of three maize varieties. From the graph, the proximate composition of three maize varieties Fat, crude fiber, and ash percentages are lower in composition compared to others. Energy has the maximum composition for three varieties, followed by carbohydrate and protein. The higher composition of energy and carbohydrate in maize varieties implies that maize is the main source of energy for humans who consume them. The daily intake of metals from maize seed food has been calculated based on the assumption that an average adult person consumes 200 g of dry maize food per day on average. The amounts of mineral intake by the person from the different forms of maize seed food are given in Table 6 below (Bull.Chem.Soc.Ethiopia.et al. 2017).

The amount of all major metals (Ca, Mg, K, and Na) that a person can get is lower than the daily recommended values; this indicates that maize alone cannot be a good source of the major metals needed for the daily requirement for the major metals. Therefore, the person must get supplementary Ca, Mg, K, and Na from other sources. The amount of Mn and Co that the man can get is also in the recommended range of the required amount. Hence, a supplementary diet is needed for these metals too. The amount of iron is very sufficient for the sample from the selected area of the study site, so no additional source of Fe is needed for those people in the three sites. The amount of Zn that a man can get from maize is in the range for those from K001, K002 and K003 (Abala Faracho wown).

Conclusion

The Soil of study area was slightly acidic, moderate level of SOC, low level of TN, low to moderate amount of P, high amount of CEC, optimum amount of exchangeable base Ca, Mg, K and Na as well as Clay to clay loam textural class. The proximate composition of three maize varieties was analyzed for fat, ash, crude fiber, protein, moisture, carbohydrate, and energy. The concentrations of three maize varieties are listed in ascending order: energy (345–357 Kcal)>carbohydrate (69.2–75.5 g/100 g)>protein (6.8–8.4%)>moisture (11.8–15.8%)> fat (3.08–4.08%)>crude fiber (1.52-2.01%)>ash percentage (1.01–1.32%). The average level of metal in the current study was ordered as follows: K (766-851 ppm)>Ca (556-642 ppm)>Mg (466-540 ppm)>Na (158-170 ppm)>Fe (33.2-45.5)>Zn (31-35.5)>Mn (2.8-3.4 ppm)>Co (0.46-0.55 ppm). The ANOVA results at the 95% confidence level suggest that there was a significant difference in the mean concentration of proximate composition and all metals among the

sampling areas. These differences could be attributed to the differences in mineral contents of soil nutrients and types as well as soil pH, SOC, CEC and other nutrient. This research shows significant differences in nutritional composition and selected essential metals among three maize varieties and provides information for an effective guide on diets and selecting the best variety for consumption. The current study concludes that from the three varieties, Shone-19 accumulates relatively higher potassium levels from macro-essential metals, higher iron levels from micro essential metals, and optimum mineral levels compared to BH540 and BH545 varieties. Among the studied varieties, Shone 19 (SH-19) maize seems to be most preferable for human and animal consumption due to its significantly high protein, ash, carbohydrate, energy, Fe, Ca, K, Mn, and Co in composition.

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